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THE IMPORTANCE OF LISTENING SKILLS FOR STUDENT'S PROFICIENT LANGUAGE

Turaboyeva Kamila

Karshi engineering and economics institute

Annotation: *As educators of English for Specific Purposes, we are aware of the importance of listening in both language and task-related situations. Authentic materials are more transferable to listening outside of the ESP classroom environment to the workplace and community.*

Key words: *recognize, key concepts, supporting details, to recognize, causes effects, to indicate*

Listening ought to be pertinent. Taking into consideration the objectives and experiences of the learners will maintain motivation and attention levels high since learners listen with a purpose and listen to things that interest them. For instance, in order for students at a worksite to comprehend new policies and procedures that are presented during staff meetings, they should be assisted in class in developing the skills necessary to recognize key concepts and supporting details, to recognize causes and effects, to indicate understanding or a lack of it, and to ask questions. Content needs to be genuine.

As educators of English for Specific Purposes, we are aware of the importance of listening in both language and task-related situations. Authentic materials are more transferable to listening outside of the ESP classroom environment to the workplace and community. Examples of these materials are workplace training DVDs, audio recordings of real workplace conversations, and TV and radio broadcasts. There should be opportunities to enhance bottom-up and top-down processing abilities. It is common knowledge that top-down activities encourage students to talk about what they already know about a subject, while bottom-up practice exercises help students gain confidence in their ability to hear and understand language elements such as words, sounds, intonation, and grammatical structures.

The final stage of teaching a text or the given topic involves post-listening activities, which cover two kinds of activities:

1. comprehension activities
2. evaluation activities [2]

Comprehension activities focus on checking understanding of English itself and interpretation of the text. Students are asked to do some question-oriented exercises which test students' comprehension and memory, and the questions are usually offered by textbooks.

Evaluation activities aim at developing students' self-evaluation strategy in order to make them more efficient listeners. In order to let students have a chance to practice oral English in a functional situation, we can have one more kind of post-listening activities: production activities, which are intended to promote students' oral ability. [3]

There are many helpful activities to choose from for developing listening skills of our ESP learners. Lund has categorized them according to responses that can be observed as comprehension checks:

1. Doing: the listener responds physically such as in Total Physical Response;
2. Choosing: the listener selects from alternatives such as pictures, objects, texts or actions;
3. Transferring: the listener transforms the message such as drawing a route on map or filling in a chart;
4. Answering: the listener answers questions about the text;
5. Condensing: the listener takes notes or makes an outline;
6. Extending: the listener goes beyond the text by continuing the the story or solving a problem;
7. Duplicating: the listener simply repeats or translates the message;
8. Conversing: the listener is an active participant in a face-to-face conversation. [4]

So, if we teach ESP learners by feeling strongly responsibility we can achieve good results. For that we should analyze the listening tasks if they are authentic or interesting or possible to their knowledge level or not and should follow the guide of the stage of every lesson.

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